

Risk of Subsequent Primary Melanoma in 68,002 five-year survivors of childhood and adolescent cancer in Europe: The PanCareSurFup cohort study

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Word count: 3,268

Word count abstract: 250

Abstract

Background: Survivors of childhood cancer are at risk of subsequent primary melanoma (SPM), but the magnitude of the risk after different childhood cancer types and beyond age 50 remains inadequately characterised. We quantified risks in the largest cohort of childhood cancer survivors worldwide.

Methods: The PanCareSurFup cohort includes 68,002 five-year childhood cancer survivors across Europe (diagnosed 1940–2008). SPM risks were quantified using standardised incidence ratios (SIRs), absolute excess risks (AERs), cumulative incidence and relative risks (RRs).

Results: Over 1,239,675 person-years, 197 SPMs were ascertained whereas 84.9 were expected (SIR=2.3, 95%CI=2.0 to 2.7). Although the SIR decreased with attained age ($P_{\text{trend}} < 0.001$), it remained increased at 2.1-fold (95%CI=1.5 to 3.1) age 50+. By age 65, cumulative incidence was 1.2% (0.8% expected). Of all cancer types, heritable retinoblastoma survivors had the greatest risk (SIR=16.5, 95% CI=10.8 to 25.3; AER=94.4, 95% CI=59.9 to 148.9), with cumulative incidence of 3.3% at age 50 and 5.5% at age 60. Survivors treated with radiotherapy had a 70% greater risk than those treated without (RR=1.7, 95% CI=1.1 to 2.7) increasing to 4-fold age 50+ (RR=3.9, 95%CI=1.1 to 13.9). For chemotherapy, no significant association was found (RR=0.9, 95%CI=0.5 to 1.6).

Conclusions: Childhood cancer survivors, particularly those with heritable retinoblastoma and those treated with radiotherapy, remain at increased risk of melanoma beyond age 50. Current survivorship guidelines focus principally on treatment history; however, our findings suggest that long-term follow-up guidelines should additionally include childhood cancer type and attained age as risk-stratifying factors, particularly where individual treatment records are unavailable.

Introduction

Since the 1970s, survival from childhood cancer has improved substantially, with five-year survival rates currently reaching 81% in Europe (1). Whilst advancements in cancer treatment have led to increases in survival, the long-term effects of treatment remain a major concern with two-thirds of survivors experiencing one or more late effects (2,3). One of the most severe late effects is the development of a subsequent primary neoplasm (SPN) with 14% of survivors experiencing an SPN by age 60 years (4). A diagnosis of melanoma is especially concerning if metastasised to distant organs due to its high mortality rate (5–8). As the population of childhood cancer survivors reaches their fifties and beyond—approaching the median age of melanoma diagnosis in the general population (59 years)(9)—even a modestly increased risk of melanoma relative to the general population could result in a substantial absolute excess risk among survivors.

Previous large-scale cohort studies have quantified the risks of subsequent primary melanomas (SPMs) among survivors of childhood cancer (4,10–14) but, to our knowledge, the largest study to date that has characterised the risk of melanoma by specific factors included 110 invasive melanomas but only 10 melanomas that occurred beyond age 50 (11). In addition, the magnitude of the risk of SPMs among specific types of childhood cancer remains poorly characterised. Hence, we conducted a retrospective cohort study involving nearly 68,000 five-year survivors of childhood cancer with nearly three times the number of melanomas beyond age 50. The principal aim of this study was to quantify the long-term risks of developing SPMs by specific factors, including childhood cancer type, sex, age at childhood cancer, treatment era, attained age, and previous treatment with radiotherapy and chemotherapy using the largest cohort of childhood cancer survivors worldwide.

Methods

PanCare childhood and adolescent cancer survivor care and follow-up studies (PanCareSurFup)

PanCare is a multidisciplinary pan-European network of professionals, researchers, childhood cancer survivors and their families. One of the main research projects of PanCare was the PanCareSurFup study. One of the principal aims of the PanCareSurFup study was to investigate the risks and causes of developing SPNs among 5-year survivors of childhood and adolescent cancer (15–17). The study includes survivors diagnosed with cancer age 0–20 years between 1940–2008, representing the largest assembled cohort of childhood cancer survivors to date. Data on individuals were collected from 13 institutions across 12 European countries including France, Hungary, Italy, the Netherlands, Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden, Slovenia, Switzerland, and the UK (**Table S1**). The data were obtained from 11 population-based cancer registries and two major hospital treatment centres. Ethical approval had already been obtained for each institution contributing to the PanCareSurFup cohort and each institution either obtained written informed consent from participants or the necessary legal permission to process individual patient data without consent.

Cohort ascertainment and childhood cancer classification

To ensure standardised classification across countries, all childhood cancers were coded according to the International Classification of Diseases for Oncology, Third Edition (ICD-O-3). For diagnoses originally coded in earlier ICD-O versions, topography and morphology codes were converted using the IARC/IACR Check and Conversion Program (18). Following this conversion, childhood cancers were then categorised into major diagnostic groups according to the International Classification of Childhood Cancer, Third Edition (ICCC-3) (19). Only malignant childhood tumours were included in the cohort except for intra-cranial benign tumours and bladder tumours. To minimise potential misclassification of a recurrence of a first primary melanoma as an SPM, we excluded individuals with childhood melanoma. We also excluded individuals with a primary diagnosis of myelodysplastic syndrome, Langerhans cell histiocytosis, or chronic myelo/lymphoproliferative disorders due to inconsistent ascertainment of these conditions across countries.

Subsequent Primary Melanomas (SPMs) ascertainment

SPMs were ascertained through linkage with multiple complementary sources including population-based national cancer registries, medical records and hospital data, national mortality records, health insurance registries, late effect clinics, and questionnaires. All SPMs were validated through pathology reports. We included only cutaneous malignant melanomas (ICD-10 code C43) if the behaviour code was malignant (ICD-O behaviour code: 3). Ocular melanomas and other non-

cutaneous sites were excluded as they are aetiologically distinct from cutaneous melanoma and there were too few (n=8) for meaningful analyses.

General population melanoma rates

For each country, general population melanoma incidence rates were obtained from the Cancer Incidence in Five Continents (CI5) database (20). For Hungary, where national data were unavailable, we used mortality-adjusted melanoma incidence rates from Slovakia (21). Where incidence rates for specific calendar years were missing, rates from the closest available year were used.

Statistical Analysis

Time-at-risk for SPMs began five years after childhood cancer diagnosis and continued until loss to follow-up, death, or study exit date. Standardised incidence ratios (SIRs) were calculated as: $SIR = \frac{\sum \text{Observed}}{\sum \text{Expected number of melanoma}}$ (22). Expected numbers were derived by accumulating person-years at risk within specific strata of the factors country, sex, age (5-year bands) and calendar year (one-year bands) and then multiplying the aggregated person-years within each stratum by the corresponding stratum specific general population melanoma incidence rate. Absolute excess risks (AERs) were calculated as: $AER = \left[\frac{(\sum \text{Observed} - \sum \text{Expected number of melanoma})}{\sum \text{Person-years at risk}} \right] \times 100,000$. The AER is an additive measure, and in this study, it quantifies the additional number of melanomas diagnosed among survivors on top of those diagnosed in the general population, per 100,000 person-years. All melanomas, including multiple primaries in the same individual, were included in SIR and AER calculations to ensure appropriate comparability with general population rates.

To account for potential confounding, we used random effects multivariable Poisson regression—with the expected number of melanomas as offset—to calculate relative risks (RRs) of melanoma by various potential explanatory factors including sex, type of childhood cancer, hereditary status for retinoblastoma survivors, age at diagnosis, decade of diagnosis, attained age, treatment with radiotherapy (yes/no) and chemotherapy (yes/no). In this context, the RR can be interpreted as a ratio of SIRs adjusted for confounders, with the lowest level of each factor acting as the reference category. For each potential explanatory factor, we fitted a separate Poisson regression model with confounder selection informed by a directed acyclic graph (DAG). This approach ensured adjustment for a theoretically justified set of confounding variables based on causal assumptions depicted in the DAG. Country was included as a random effect in the Poisson regression model to account for potential between-country heterogeneity arising from unmeasured

variation in, for example, genetic background, healthcare systems, diagnostic practices, and treatment protocols.

The cumulative incidence of a first SPM was calculated by attained age, accounting for death as a competing risk (23,24). The expected cumulative incidence was estimated by the conditional method using general population melanoma incidence rates (25).

Likelihood-ratio tests were used to calculate p-values for heterogeneity and linear trend. Variables were coded as consecutive integer values (e.g. 1,2,3,4 for attained age) and included in the models as factors for heterogeneity tests and as continuous variables for trend tests. A two-sided significance level was set to less than 5%. All analyses were conducted using Stata version 18.0.

Results

Cohort characteristics

The cohort comprised 68,002 individuals followed-up for 1,239,675 person-years, with a median follow-up of 16.3 years (IQR= 6.9–27.3). Loss to follow-up did not exceed 6% in any country (**Table S1**). Among 188 survivors, 197 SPMs were observed, with nine survivors developing more than one melanoma. The median attained age at cohort exit was 30.2 years (IQR=21.0–40.4). The median latency to SPM development was 26.5 years (IQR=19.2–36.5) (**Table S2**). The most common anatomical sites were the trunk (36.0%) and lower limb (27.9%). The most frequent type of melanoma was superficial spreading melanoma (50.3%) (**Table 1**).

Risk by type of childhood cancer

Overall, survivors were 2.3 times more likely to develop an SPM than expected (SIR=2.3, 95%CI= 2.0 to 2.7), with 9 melanomas per 100,000 person-years in excess of that expected in the general population (AER=9.0, 95%CI= 7.1 to 11.6). In terms of the SIR, survivors of heritable retinoblastoma were at greatest risk (SIR=16.5, 95%CI= 10.8 to 25.3) followed by non-heritable retinoblastoma (SIR=3.2, 95%CI= 1.5 to 6.7), neuroblastoma (SIR=2.8, 95%CI= 1.4 to 5.6), germ cell and gonadal neoplasm (SIR=2.6, 95%CI= 1.4 to 4.7), and non-Hodgkin lymphoma (SIR=2.5, 95%CI= 1.4 to 4.4) survivors. Other childhood cancers, except osteosarcoma showed elevated risks although of lesser magnitude (**Table 2**). The greatest AERs were found among survivors of heritable retinoblastoma (AER=94.4, 95% CI= 59.9 to 148.9) and non-heritable retinoblastoma (AER=15.3, 95%CI= 5.2 to 45.1). Multivariable analyses revealed that heritable retinoblastoma survivors were at 5.2-fold greater risk than non-heritable retinoblastoma survivors (95%CI= 2.2 to 12.2).

Risk by attained age

The SIR decreased with increasing attained age (P-trend<0.001) but was still 2.0-fold elevated (95%CI= 1.4 to 2.7) at ages 40-49 years and 2.1-fold (95%CI= 1.5 to 3.1) beyond age 50 years. Multivariable analyses confirmed this pattern, showing a 70% decrease in the RR from ages 5-19 years to 50+ years (**Table 2**). Even after excluding retinoblastoma survivors, this trend persisted (P-trend<0.001) with individuals aged 40–49 and 50+ years at 60% (SIR=1.6, 95%CI= 1.1 to 2.3) and 80% (SIR=1.8, 95%CI= 1.2 to 2.7) elevated risk, respectively (**Table 3**). Conversely, the overall AER increased with attained age from 4.4 (95%CI= 2.7 to 7.3) at ages 5-19 years to 16.4 (95%CI= 8.6 to 31.0) at ages 40-49 and 30.6 (95%CI= 15.4 to 60.9) age 50+ years (P-trend<0.001) (**Table 2**). This trend also persisted after excluding retinoblastoma survivors (P-trend<0.001) (**Table 3**).

Cumulative Incidence

The cumulative incidence of SPM increased with attained age from 0.1% at age 20 to 1.2% at age 65 years (**Figure 1**). Heritable retinoblastoma survivors showed the sharpest increase: 0.5% (95%CI= 0.1% to 1.3%) by age 20; 3.3% (95%CI= 1.9% to 5.2%) by age 50, and 5.5% (95%CI= 3.0% to 9.2%) by age 60. The cumulative incidence reached 2.2% (95% CI= 0.6% to 5.8%) by age 60 among leukaemia survivors and 0.8% (95% CI= 0.5% to 1.3%) by age 55 among lymphoma survivors. The expected risk in the general population was 0.6% by age 60 (**Figure 2**).

Risk by previous treatment

Survivors treated with radiotherapy had a 70% increased risk compared to those treated without radiotherapy (RR=1.7, 95%CI= 1.1 to 2.7) (**Table 2**). This association was strongest in survivors aged 50+ years (RR=3.9, 95%CI= 1.1 to 13.9) (**Table S3**). For prior chemotherapy no statistically significant association was found compared to no chemotherapy (RR=0.9, 95%CI= 0.5 to 1.6) (**Table 2**).

Discussion

Main findings

In this largest-ever cohort study of childhood cancer survivors, we provide for the first time robust estimates of increased relative and absolute excess risks of SPMs beyond 50 years and among a wide spectrum of type of childhood cancer survivors. The risk of developing melanoma relative to the general population decreases with attained age but remains increased even beyond age 50 years. Survivors of heritable retinoblastoma are at greatest risk with a 5.5% absolute risk by age 60 years. Additionally, survivors treated with radiotherapy are at increased risk of developing SPM, even beyond age 50, compared to survivors treated without radiotherapy.

Risk by attained age

Few previous studies evaluated SPM risk by attained age. The largest previous study, conducted in North America, reported elevated SIRs and AERs for melanoma at ages 40–49 years (11), consistent with our SIR (2.0, 95%CI= 1.4 to 2.7) and AER (16.4, 95%CI= 8.6 to 31.0) at the same ages. To our knowledge, that study is the only one to have reported risk estimates beyond age 50 years; however, only 10 melanomas were observed at these ages, resulting in an increased but statistically insignificant SIR (1.3, 95%CI= 0.7 to 2.7) and AER (16.6, 95%CI= -15.1 to 79.2). In the present study, with greater statistical power, we identified a downward trend in SIRs and an upward trend in AERs with attained age, with both remaining significantly elevated beyond age 50.

Risk by type of childhood cancer

Few previous studies reported SIRs and/or AERs of melanoma by type of childhood cancer and most included few melanomas (12,26), an exception is retinoblastoma (27–32). To our knowledge, SIRs have been reported for only five cancer types: soft tissue sarcoma (observed melanomas=2), Hodgkin lymphoma (n=6), leukaemia (n=2), and germ cell tumours (n=2), all from the same study (12), as well as retinoblastoma (n≤40) (27–32). Our study expands this evidence with eight-fold more observations of melanoma for soft-tissue sarcoma, three-fold for Hodgkin lymphoma, 14-fold for leukaemia, and five-fold for gonadal and germ cell tumours. The SIRs reported in the previous study (12) were generally consistent with our findings. We ascertained 36 melanomas after retinoblastoma, of which 21 were heritable. All previous large-scale cohort studies consistently reported substantially elevated SIRs of melanoma following heritable retinoblastoma (27–32) with our SIR (SIR=16.5, 95%CI: 10.8 to 25.3) being consistent with all except the SIR reported by Marees *et al.* (27) which was substantially greater (SIR=50.8, 95%CI:27.0 to 86.8). Additionally, we report, to our knowledge for the first time, elevated SIRs and AERs for CNS tumour,

Wilms tumour, neuroblastoma, and non-Hodgkin lymphoma with sufficient melanomas to reliably quantify the risk in these groups. Although heritable retinoblastoma survivors showed substantially greater risks than all other cancer types, the consistently elevated risk across almost all childhood cancer types (SIR ~2-fold) suggests that melanoma surveillance may warrant consideration for childhood cancer survivors more broadly, not only for heritable retinoblastoma survivors for whom surveillance is already recommended (33).

Approximately 10% of childhood cancers involve cancer predisposition syndromes (34,35), which may increase also subsequent melanoma risk (36,37) independent of prior treatment. Heritable retinoblastoma has been associated with developing subsequent osteosarcoma and soft-tissue sarcoma, but also melanoma (38). The elevated melanoma risk in heritable retinoblastoma survivors is likely driven by germline inactivation of the RB1 tumour suppressor gene, which plays a central role in cell cycle regulation and predisposes to multiple subsequent neoplasm types, including melanoma. In our study, heritable retinoblastoma survivors had five-times greater risks than non-heritable survivors although non-heritable retinoblastoma survivors were also at increased risk. However, this finding was based on only seven melanomas in non-heritable retinoblastoma and should be interpreted cautiously. Genetic testing may not have been routinely performed for all retinoblastoma survivors in our historical cohort and thus heritable status may not always definitively have been determined. Consequently, some heritable retinoblastoma survivors may have been misclassified as non-heritable potentially inflating risks among non-heritable retinoblastoma survivors. The comparable magnitude of risk irrespective of radiotherapy exposure further supports genetic susceptibility as the predominant driver of melanoma risk in heritable retinoblastoma survivors. Notably, heritable retinoblastoma survivors showed similarly elevated SIRs regardless of radiotherapy treatment (16.7 with vs. 13.6 without radiotherapy; Table 2), although the latter estimate is based on only two melanomas.

Other cancer predisposition syndromes associated with melanoma include familial atypical multiple mole melanoma (FAMMM) and Li-Fraumeni syndrome (TP53 mutations) (39,40). FAMMM is likely most prevalent among survivors with a first primary melanoma; by excluding individuals with a melanoma as their childhood cancer, the percentage of survivors with FAMMM in our study is likely to be small. Li-Fraumeni syndrome may also be associated with melanoma, but we lacked genetic data to assess the contribution of Li-Fraumeni or other genetic syndromes.

Risk by prior cancer treatment

Our finding of a 1.7 increased RR among survivors treated with radiotherapy versus those without, complements those from Rotz *et al.* (11), who showed a dose–response relationship with 2-fold

increased risks for body parts receiving cumulative radiation doses exceeding 40 Gy exposure compared to no exposure. Most previous studies focusing on melanoma as a subsequent primary neoplasm could not detect an association between melanoma and treatment with radiotherapy (10,12,14,41), although Guerin *et al.* (41) found a non-significantly increased risk for doses exceeding 15 Gy. Likely, the risk is only evident after exposure to high doses of radiation and most previous studies lacked statistical power to detect an association.

Regarding chemotherapy, we did not find a significant association with the risk of melanoma. Turcotte *et al.* (42) did find a 2-fold increased risk among survivors treated with chemotherapy only in the CCSS cohort and in the most recent CCSS (11) an increased risk associated with a cyclophosphamide equivalent dose exceeding 20,000 mg/m² and any dose of bleomycin was found. However, we were only able to investigate the risk of melanoma by whether survivors had received any chemotherapy or not, but not by cumulative doses of drug groups or individual cytotoxic agents.

Clinical implications

We demonstrate that survivors remain at increased risk of SPM throughout all the ages investigated and that the AER is greatest above age 50. The 6th version of the Long-Term Follow-Up Guidelines for Survivors of Childhood, Adolescent, and Young Adult Cancers from the Children's Oncology Group recommends periodic evaluations, including annual dermatological examinations and monthly skin self-examinations, as well as sun protection and oncology consultations (43), but these recommendations are currently limited to individuals with a history of hematopoietic stem cell transplantation (HSCT), radiotherapy, experience of any type of skin cancer or family history of skin cancer. Similarly, the Dutch guideline for follow-up after childhood cancer—more than 5 years after diagnosis updated in 2023, indicates individuals with history of any type of radiotherapy and HSCT as people at risk of later melanoma (44). Additionally, the 2024 update of PanCare Follow-Up Recommendations for Surveillance of Late Effects suggested self-examination at least every six months and a skin examination at least every two years after five years in individuals with a history of any radiotherapy and or HSCT (45). There are currently no specific recommendations tailored to survivors based on the type of childhood cancer or attained age group. While treatment-related risk factors have been addressed in existing guidelines, first primary tumour specific risks have not yet been incorporated. Given that detailed treatment histories are often unavailable, particularly for older survivors in long-term follow-up due to missing or incomplete records, our findings could enhance guidelines by including childhood cancer type and attained age as an additional risk stratifying factor.

We suggest that guidelines consider incorporating regular dermatological examinations into the long-term follow-up care for these high-risk subgroups to facilitate early detection of melanoma (and non-melanoma skin cancers). Furthermore, we suggest general melanoma risk reduction strategies, such as regular skin self-examinations, sun protection, and avoidance of intermittent sun exposure, for all survivors.

Study limitations

Our study has several limitations. We lacked information on individual-level melanoma risk factors such as genetic predisposition (e.g. CDKN2A mutations), HSCT, sun exposure, skin phototype, and naevus count. These factors are not routinely captured in population-based cancer registries and would typically affect survivors and the general population, similarly, minimising potential bias. Additionally, we lacked detailed treatment data precluding assessment of risks by cumulative doses of specific chemotherapy agents, cumulative doses of radiation or specific radiation fields. We could only investigate risks by whether survivors had received radiotherapy, but not by the exact anatomical site of the radiation treatment. While this may have introduced misclassification, it would likely attenuate rather than inflate our risk estimates. Despite these limitations, the association we identified between radiotherapy and melanoma is consistent with findings from Rotz et al. (11) using more detailed treatment data from the North American CCSS. Furthermore, detailed pathological characteristics of the melanomas, such as Breslow thickness and staging, were not available centrally due to data protection constraints inherent to multi-country studies and could therefore not be investigated.

Conclusion

In conclusion, childhood cancer survivors, particularly heritable retinoblastoma survivors and those who received radiotherapy, remain at risk of melanoma beyond age 50 years. Current guidelines for melanoma risk mainly focus on treatment history. However, our findings suggest that guidelines, particularly long-term follow-up ones, could be enhanced by including childhood cancer type and attained age as additional risk stratifying factors, particularly when individual treatment histories are not available.

Acknowledgment

We are very grateful to the childhood cancer survivors whose information was used for PanCareSurFup. We also would like to thank the following individuals from each country for their contribution to data preparation: France: Angela Jackson, Florent Dayet, Amar Kahlouche, Fara Diop, Sylvie Challeton, Martine Labbé, Isao Kobayashi. Italy: Maura Massimino, Silvia Caruso, Vera Morsellino, Claudia Casella, Lucia Miligi, Anita Andreano, Andrea Biondi and the AIRTUM working group. The Netherlands: Dutch Childhood Oncology Group LATER; Wim Tissing, Marry van den Heuvel-Eibrink, Eline van Dulmen, Jacqueline Loonen, Dorine Bresters, Birgitta Versluys. Slovenia: Tina Žagar. Sweden: Ingemar Andersson, Susanne Nordenfelt. Switzerland: Elisabeth Kiraly, Vera Mitter, Shelag Redmond and the Swiss Paediatric Oncology Group (www.spog.ch). UK: Julie Kelly. The funders had no role in the design of the study; the collection, analysis, or interpretation of the data; or the writing of the manuscript and decision to submit it for publication.

Funding

The PanCareSurFup consortium and related work was supported by the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development, and demonstration under grant agreement no. 257505. Additional financial support was received from:

- Children with Cancer UK (grant no: 20457).
- The Dutch Cancer Society (DCOG2011-5027 and UVA2012-5517).
- The Dietmar Hopp Foundation.
- The Foundation Force de recherche sur le cancer de l'enfant (FORCE).
- The Fondo Chiara Rama ONLUS.
- The French Association for Cancer Research (ARC).
- The French National Agency for Research (ANR) (Hope-Epi project).
- The French National Cancer Institute (INCA).
- The Italian Association for Cancer Research and the Compagnia San Paolo.
- The Norwegian Childhood Cancer Foundation.
- Pfizer Foundation for Children and Adolescent Health.
- Slovenian Research Agency.
- The Swedish Childhood Cancer Fund.
- The Swiss Cancer League (KLS-3412-02-2014, KLS-3886-02-2016, KLS-5432-08-2021).
- The Swiss Cancer Research foundation (KFS02783-02-2011, KFS-4157-02-2017, KLA/KFS-4825-01-2019, KFS-4722-02-2019, KFS5302-02-2021).
- The Swiss National Science Foundation (PDFMP3_141775).

Conflict of Interest

No conflicts of interest were reported by any authors. Where authors are identified as personnel of the International Agency for Research on Cancer/World Health Organization, the authors alone are responsible for the views expressed in this article and they do not necessarily represent the decisions, policy, or views of the International Agency for Research on Cancer/World Health Organization.

Data Availability Statement

Access to anonymised data may be granted under conditions agreed with the relevant (local) legal and research ethics committees and with appropriate data sharing agreements and permissions from each data provider in place. Any data sharing would have to comply with the EU General Data Protection Regulation. The data that support the findings of this study are not publicly available due to privacy and ethical restrictions. Aggregated data in the form of tables may be available on reasonable request.

References

1. Botta L, Gatta G, Capocaccia R, Stiller C, Cañete A, Maso LD, et al. Long-term survival and cure fraction estimates for childhood cancer in Europe (EUROCORE-6): results from a population-based study. *Lancet Oncol*. 2022 Dec 1;23(12):12. doi:10.1016/S1470-2045(22)00637-4 PubMed PMID: 36400102.
2. Geenen MM, Cardous-Ubbink MC, Kremer LCM, van den Bos C, van der Pal HJH, Heinen RC, et al. Medical assessment of adverse health outcomes in long-term survivors of childhood cancer. *JAMA*. 2007 Jun 27;297(24):24. doi:10.1001/jama.297.24.2705 PubMed PMID: 17595271.
3. Oeffinger KC, Mertens AC, Sklar CA, Kawashima T, Hudson MM, Meadows AT, et al. Chronic health conditions in adult survivors of childhood cancer. *N Engl J Med*. 2006 Oct 12;355(15):15. doi:10.1056/NEJMsa060185 PubMed PMID: 17035650.
4. Reulen RC, Frobisher C, Winter DL, Kelly J, Lancashire ER, Stiller CA, et al. Long-term risks of subsequent primary neoplasms among survivors of childhood cancer. *JAMA*. 2011 Jun 8;305(22):22. doi:10.1001/jama.2011.747 PubMed PMID: 21642683.
5. Bataille V, de Vries E. Melanoma: Part 1: Epidemiology, Risk Factors, and Prevention. *BMJ*. 2008;337(7681):7681.
6. Forsea AM. Melanoma Epidemiology and Early Detection in Europe: Diversity and Disparities. *Dermatol Pract Concept*. 2020 Jun 29;10(3):3. doi:10.5826/dpc.1003a33 PubMed PMID: 32642304; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC7319793.
7. Aggarwal P, Knabel P, Fleischer AB. United States burden of melanoma and non-melanoma skin cancer from 1990 to 2019. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2021 Aug;85(2):2. doi:10.1016/j.jaad.2021.03.109 PubMed PMID: 33852922.
8. Saginala K, Barsouk A, Aluru JS, Rawla P, Barsouk A. Epidemiology of Melanoma. *Med Sci*. 2021 Oct 20;9(4):4. doi:10.3390/medsci9040063 PubMed PMID: 34698235; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC8544364.
9. Shah R, Patel N, Patel Y, Toscani M, Barone J, Weber PF. Age Demographics of Subjects Enrolled in Global, Interventional Phase 3 Melanoma Clinical Trials. *Ther Innov Regul Sci*. 2022;56(2):2. doi:10.1007/s43441-021-00362-0 PubMed PMID: 35001359; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC8854139.
10. Pappo AS, Armstrong GT, Liu W, Srivastava DK, McDonald A, Leisenring WM, et al. Melanoma as a subsequent neoplasm in adult survivors of childhood cancer: a report from the childhood cancer survivor study. *Pediatr Blood Cancer*. 2013 Mar;60(3):3. doi:10.1002/pbc.24266 PubMed PMID: 22887858; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC3538914.
11. Rotz SJ, Stratton K, Leisenring WM, Smith SA, Howell RM, Bates JE, et al. Melanoma Among Adult Survivors of Childhood Cancer: A Report From the Childhood Cancer Survivor Study. *J Clin Oncol Off J Am Soc Clin Oncol*. 2025 Jan 8;JCO2401519. doi:10.1200/JCO-24-01519 PubMed PMID: 39778123.

12. Inskip PD, Curtis RE. New malignancies following childhood cancer in the United States, 1973-2002. *Int J Cancer*. 2007 Nov 15;121(10):10. doi:10.1002/ijc.22827 PubMed PMID: 17557301.
13. Olsen JH, Möller T, Anderson H, Langmark F, Sankila R, Tryggvadóttir L, et al. Lifelong cancer incidence in 47,697 patients treated for childhood cancer in the Nordic countries. *J Natl Cancer Inst*. 2009 Jun 3;101(11):11. doi:10.1093/jnci/djp104 PubMed PMID: 19470947.
14. Teepen JC, Kok JL, Kremer LC, Tissing WJE, van den Heuvel-Eibrink MM, Loonen JJ, et al. Long-Term Risk of Skin Cancer Among Childhood Cancer Survivors: A DCOG-LATER Cohort Study. *J Natl Cancer Inst*. 2019 Aug 1;111(8):8. doi:10.1093/jnci/djy212 PubMed PMID: 30802904; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC6695299.
15. Byrne J, Alessi D, Allodji RS, Bagnasco F, Bárdi E, Bautz A, et al. The PanCareSurFup consortium: research and guidelines to improve lives for survivors of childhood cancer. *Eur J Cancer Oxf Engl* 1990. 2018 Nov;103:238–48. doi:10.1016/j.ejca.2018.08.017 PubMed PMID: 30286417.
16. Hjorth L, Haupt R, Skinner R, Grabow D, Byrne J, Karner S, et al. Survivorship after childhood cancer: PanCare: a European Network to promote optimal long-term care. *Eur J Cancer Oxf Engl* 1990. 2015 Jul;51(10):10. doi:10.1016/j.ejca.2015.04.002 PubMed PMID: 25958037; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC5916870.
17. Grabow D, Kaiser M, Hjorth L, Byrne J, Alessi D, Allodji RS, et al. The PanCareSurFup cohort of 83,333 five-year survivors of childhood cancer: a cohort from 12 European countries. *Eur J Epidemiol*. 2018 Mar;33(3):3. doi:10.1007/s10654-018-0370-3 PubMed PMID: 29497894; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC5889790.
18. Ferlay J, Burkhard C, Whelan S, Parkin DM. IARC/IACR Tools for Cancer Registries. Check and conversion programs for cancer registries (I). [IARC technical]. Lyon; 2005. p. 1–40. Report No.: 42.
19. Steliarova-Foucher E, Stiller C, Lacour B, Kaatsch P. International Classification of Childhood Cancer, third edition. *Cancer*. 2005 Apr 1;103(7):7. doi:10.1002/cncr.20910 PubMed PMID: 15712273.
20. CI5: Cancer Incidence in Five Continents [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Jul 17]. Available from: <https://ci5.iarc.fr/>
21. Ferlay J, Autier P, Boniol M, Heanue M, Colombet M, Boyle P. Estimates of the cancer incidence and mortality in Europe in 2006. *Ann Oncol Off J Eur Soc Med Oncol*. 2007 Mar;18(3):581–92. doi:10.1093/annonc/mdl498 PubMed PMID: 17287242.
22. Breslow NE, Day NE. Statistical methods in cancer research. Volume II--The design and analysis of cohort studies. *IARC Sci Publ*. 1987;(82):82. PubMed PMID: 3329634.
23. Gooley TA, Leisenring W, Crowley J, Storer BE. Estimation of failure probabilities in the presence of competing risks: new representations of old estimators. *Stat Med*. 1999 Mar 30;18(6):6. doi:10.1002/(sici)1097-0258(19990330)18:6%3C695::aid-sim60%3E3.0.co;2-o PubMed PMID: 10204198.
24. Coviello V, Boggess M. Cumulative Incidence Estimation in the Presence of Competing Risks. *Stata J*. 2004 Jun 1;4(2):2. doi:10.1177/1536867X0400400201

25. Therneau TM, Grambsch PM. Modeling Survival Data: Extending the Cox Model. Springer Science & Business Media; 2013. 356 p.
26. Socié G, Curtis RE, Deeg HJ, Sobocinski KA, Filipovich AH, Travis LB, et al. New malignant diseases after allogeneic marrow transplantation for childhood acute leukemia. *J Clin Oncol Off J Am Soc Clin Oncol*. 2000 Jan;18(2):2. doi:10.1200/JCO.2000.18.2.348 PubMed PMID: 10637249.
27. Marees T, Moll AC, Imhof SM, de Boer MR, Ringens PJ, van Leeuwen FE. Risk of second malignancies in survivors of retinoblastoma: more than 40 years of follow-up. *J Natl Cancer Inst*. 2008 Dec 17;100(24):24. doi:10.1093/jnci/djn394 PubMed PMID: 19066271.
28. Kleinerman RA, Tucker MA, Tarone RE, Abramson DH, Seddon JM, Stovall M, et al. Risk of new cancers after radiotherapy in long-term survivors of retinoblastoma: an extended follow-up. *J Clin Oncol Off J Am Soc Clin Oncol*. 2005 Apr 1;23(10):10. doi:10.1200/JCO.2005.05.054 PubMed PMID: 15800318.
29. Kleinerman RA, Yu CL, Little MP, Li Y, Abramson D, Seddon J, et al. Variation of second cancer risk by family history of retinoblastoma among long-term survivors. *J Clin Oncol Off J Am Soc Clin Oncol*. 2012 Mar 20;30(9):9. doi:10.1200/JCO.2011.37.0239 PubMed PMID: 22355046; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC3341108.
30. Kleinerman RA, Schonfeld SJ, Abramson DH, Francis JH, Seddon JM, Morton LM, et al. Increased Risk of Skin Cancer in 1,851 Long-Term Retinoblastoma Survivors. *J Invest Dermatol*. 2021 Dec;141(12):12. doi:10.1016/j.jid.2021.05.021 PubMed PMID: 34153328; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC9472549.
31. MacCarthy A, Bayne AM, Brownbill PA, Bunch KJ, Diggins NL, Draper GJ, et al. Second and subsequent tumours among 1927 retinoblastoma patients diagnosed in Britain 1951–2004. *Br J Cancer*. 2013 Jun 25;108(12):2455–63. doi:10.1038/bjc.2013.228 PubMed PMID: 23674091; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC3694232.
32. Gregersen PA, Olsen MH, Urbak SF, Funding M, Dalton SO, Overgaard J, et al. Incidence and Mortality of Second Primary Cancers in Danish Patients With Retinoblastoma, 1943-2013. *JAMA Netw Open*. 2020 Oct 22;3(10):e2022126. doi:10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.22126
33. Tonorezos ES, Friedman DN, Barnea D, Bosscha MI, Chantada G, Dommering CJ, et al. Recommendations for Long-Term Follow-up of Adults with Heritable Retinoblastoma. *Ophthalmology*. 2020 Nov;127(11):1549–57. doi:10.1016/j.ophtha.2020.05.024
34. Bakhuizen JJ, Hopman SMJ, Bosscha MI, Dommering CJ, van den Heuvel-Eibrink MM, Hol JA, et al. Assessment of Cancer Predisposition Syndromes in a National Cohort of Children With a Neoplasm. *JAMA Netw Open*. 2023 Feb 1;6(2):e2254157. doi:10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2022.54157 PubMed PMID: 36735256; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC9898819.
35. Parsons DW, Roy A, Yang Y, Wang T, Scollon S, Bergstrom K, et al. Diagnostic Yield of Clinical Tumor and Germline Whole-Exome Sequencing for Children With Solid Tumors. *JAMA Oncol*. 2016 May 1;2(5):616–24. doi:10.1001/jamaoncol.2015.5699 PubMed PMID: 26822237; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC5471125.

36. Wang Z, Wilson CL, Easton J, Thrasher A, Mulder H, Liu Q, et al. Genetic Risk for Subsequent Neoplasms Among Long-Term Survivors of Childhood Cancer. *J Clin Oncol Off J Am Soc Clin Oncol*. 2018 Jul 10;36(20):20. doi:10.1200/JCO.2018.77.8589 PubMed PMID: 29847298; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC6036620.
37. Chen C, Qin N, Wang M, Dong Q, Tithi SS, Hui Y, et al. Cancer germline predisposing variants and late mortality from subsequent malignant neoplasms among long-term childhood cancer survivors: a report from the St Jude Lifetime Cohort and the Childhood Cancer Survivor Study. *Lancet Oncol*. 2023 Oct;24(10):10. doi:10.1016/S1470-2045(23)00403-5 PubMed PMID: 37797633; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC10712938.
38. Moll AC, Imhof SM, Bouter LM, Tan KEWP. Second primary tumors in patients with retinoblastoma a review of the literature. *Ophthalmic Genet*. 1997 Jan 1;18(1):27–34. doi:10.3109/13816819709057880
39. Frebourg T, Bajalica Lagercrantz S, Oliveira C, Magenheimer R, Evans DG. Guidelines for the Li–Fraumeni and heritable TP53-related cancer syndromes. *Eur J Hum Genet*. 2020 Oct;28(10):1379–86. doi:10.1038/s41431-020-0638-4
40. Tucker MA. Melanoma Epidemiology. *Hematol Oncol Clin North Am*. 2009 Jun;23(3):3. doi:10.1016/j.hoc.2009.03.010 PubMed PMID: 19464592; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC3234163.
41. Guérin S, Dupuy A, Anderson H, Shamsaldin A, Svahn-Tapper G, Moller T, et al. Radiation dose as a risk factor for malignant melanoma following childhood cancer. *Eur J Cancer Oxf Engl* 1990. 2003 Nov;39(16):16. doi:10.1016/s0959-8049(03)00663-4 PubMed PMID: 14556931.
42. Turcotte LM, Liu Q, Yasui Y, Henderson TO, Gibson TM, Leisenring W, et al. Chemotherapy and Risk of Subsequent Malignant Neoplasms in the Childhood Cancer Survivor Study Cohort. *J Clin Oncol*. 2019 Dec 1;37(34):34. doi:10.1200/JCO.19.00129 PubMed PMID: 31622130; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC7001784.
43. Children’s Oncology Group [Internet]. [cited 2025 Aug 20]. Available from: <https://www.survivorshipguidelines.org/>
44. SKION: Richtlijn follow-up na kinderkanker Update 2023 (versie 1) [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jun 12]. Available from: <https://prinsesmaxima.iprova.nl/Portal/#/document/9409f33e-3205-4c25-a86b-682e8b01be79>
45. Updated-PanCareFollowUp-Recommendations-for-long-term-follow-up-April-2024_Final-3.0.pdf [Internet]. [cited 2025 Oct 15]. Available from: https://www.pancare.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/Updated-PanCareFollowUp-Recommendations-for-long-term-follow-up-April-2024_Final-3.0.pdf

Tables

Table 1. Cohort characteristics and subsequent primary melanoma ascertainment among 68,002 five-year childhood cancer survivors in the PanCareSurFup study.

Characteristics	Entire cohort, No. (%) ^a	SPM, No. (%) ^a
All survivors	68002 (100)	197 (100)
Sex:		
Male	37182 (54.3)	81 (41.1)
Female	30820 (45.7)	116 (58.9)
Childhood cancer type:		
Leukaemia	16646 (24.5)	29 (14.7)
Hodgkin lymphoma	6046 (8.9)	17 (8.6)
Non-Hodgkin lymphoma	4078 (6.0)	12 (6.1)
CNS tumour	14592 (21.5)	27 (13.7)
Neuroblastoma	3178 (4.7)	8 (4.1)
Retinoblastoma:	2590 (3.8)	36 (18.3)
Hereditary	714 (1.0)	21 (10.7)
Non-hereditary	1013 (1.5)	7 (3.6)
Un-known	863 (1.3)	8 (4.1)
Wilms tumour	4783 (7.0)	13 (6.6)
Osteosarcoma	3173 (4.7)	5 (2.5)
Soft-tissue sarcoma	4531 (6.7)	17 (8.6)
Germ cell and gonadal neoplasm	2721 (4.0)	11 (5.6)
Other ^b	5664 (8.3)	22 (11.2)
Data provider country:		
France	3130 (4.6)	8 (4.1)
Hungary	4869 (7.2)	1 (0.5)
Italy	8815 (13.0)	6 (3.0)
Netherlands	6022 (8.9)	22 (11.2)
Denmark	4615 (6.8)	19 (9.6)
Sweden	7418 (10.9)	13 (6.6)
Norway	3537 (5.2)	9 (4.6)
Finland	6056 (8.9)	19 (9.6)
Iceland	261 (0.4)	0
Slovenia	1221 (1.8)	0
Switzerland	4239 (6.2)	4 (2.0)
UK	17819 (26.2)	96 (48.7)
Age at prior treatment (years):		
0-4	26603 (39.1)	84 (42.6)
5-9	15611 (23.0)	39 (19.8)
10-14	15196 (22.3)	49 (24.9)
15-19	10592 (15.6)	25 (12.7)
Decade of childhood cancer diagnosis:		
<1970	8715 (12.8)	70 (35.5)
1970-79	13246 (19.5)	64 (32.5)
1980-89	20506 (30.2)	45 (22.8)
1990-1999	18843 (27.7)	17 (8.6)
2000-2008	6692 (9.8)	1 (0.5)
Attained age (year):		
5-19	15352 (22.6)	21 (10.7)
20-29	18424 (27.1)	49 (24.9)
30-39	16707 (24.6)	59 (29.9)
40-49	10720 (15.8)	39 (19.8)
50+	6799 (9.9)	29 (14.7)
Body site (ICD-10 Code classification)		
Above neck ^c	n/a	24 (12.2)
Trunk (C43.5)	n/a	71 (36.0)
Upper limb (C43.6)	n/a	37 (18.8)
Lower limb (C43.7)	n/a	55 (27.9)
Overlapping (C43.8)	n/a	1 (0.5)

Table 1. (Continued)

Characteristics	Entire cohort, No. (%)	SPM, No. (%)
Type of malignancy (ICD-O-3 Code classification)		
Malignant melanoma, NOS (87203)	n/a	78 (39.6)
Nodular melanoma (87213)	n/a	13 (6.6)
Amelanotic melanoma (87303)	n/a	1 (0.5)
Lentigo maligna melanoma (87423)	n/a	3 (1.5)
Superficial spreading melanoma (87433)	n/a	99 (50.3)
Malignant melanoma in giant pigmented nevus (87613)	n/a	2 (1.0)
Initial radiotherapy ^d		
Yes	21,106 (57.1)	89 (71.8)
No	15,852 (42.9)	35 (28.2)
Initial chemotherapy ^d		
Yes	30,947 (74.5)	62 (54.4)
No	10,612 (25.5)	52 (45.6)

Abbreviations: SPM=subsequent primary melanoma; PanCareSurFup=PanCare childhood and adolescent cancer Survivor care and follow-up studies; CNS=central nervous system; NOS=not otherwise specified

a: Counts for the PanCareSurFup cohort are based on the total number of individual survivors. Counts for SPM are based on the total number of SPM observations.

b: Included non-melanoma skin cancers, thyroid carcinomas, other and unspecified carcinomas, unspecified lymphoma, nasopharyngeal carcinoma, renal carcinomas, other peripheral nervous cell tumours, other and unspecified malignant neoplasms.

c: Included eye (C43.1), ear (C43.2), other part of face (C43.3), and scalp and neck (C43.4). n/a = not applicable

d: 21,887 individuals from Nordic countries (Denmark, Sweden, Norway, Finland, Iceland) were excluded due to lack of treatment data.

Table 2. SIR, AER and RR of SPM in all survivors and by whether treated with or without radiotherapy.

Factor	All Survivors				With Radiotherapy ^a			Without Radiotherapy		
	O/E	SIR (95% CI)	AER (95% CI)	RR ^b (95% CI)	O/E	SIR (95% CI)	AER (95% CI)	O/E	SIR (95% CI)	AER (95% CI)
Overall	197/84.9	2.3 (2.0 to 2.7)	9.0 (7.1 to 11.6)		89/34.9	2.6 (2.1 to 3.1)	11.1 (7.9 to 15.6)	35/18.2	1.9 (1.4 to 2.7)	6.0 (3.0 to 11.9)
Sex ^{b1}										
Male	81/35.6	2.3 (1.8 to 2.8)	6.8 (4.6 to 10.0)	1.0 (ref.)	38/15.0	2.5 (1.8 to 3.5)	8.6 (5.1 to 14.6)	12/7.4	1.6 (0.9 to 2.9)	3.1 (0.7 to 13.4)
Female	116/49.3	2.4 (2.0 to 2.8)	11.6 (8.5 to 16.0)	1.0 (0.8 to 1.4)	51/19.8	2.6 (2.0 to 3.4)	14.1 (9.0 to 22.0)	23/10.8	2.1 (1.4 to 3.2)	9.3 (4.3 to 20.1)
P-heterogeneity		.81	.03	.81		.94	.16		.45	.14
Childhood cancer types										
Leukaemia	29/13.7	2.1 (1.5 to 3.0)	5.9 (3.0 to 11.8)		19/9.4	2.0 (1.3 to 3.2)	6.3 (2.6 to 15.4)	4/2.3	1.8 (0.7 to 4.7)	3.5 (0.4 to 33.9)
Hodgkin lymphoma	17/8.0	2.1 (1.3 to 3.4)	9.1 (3.7 to 22.4)		7/3.8	1.8 (0.9 to 3.8)	6.7 (1.3 to 34.5)	1/0.8	1.2 (0.2 to 8.5)	1.6 (0.0 to *)
NHL ^c	12/4.9	2.5 (1.4 to 4.4)	10.2 (3.9 to 26.3)		5/2.1	2.4 (1.0 to 5.8)	11.4 (2.5 to 51.1)	1/1.1	0.9 (0.1 to 6.5)	0.0
CNS tumour	27/19.2	1.4 (1.0 to 2.1)	3.0 (0.8 to 10.9)		9/6.9	1.3 (0.7 to 2.5)	2.2 (0.1 to 37.8)	6/4.2	1.4 (0.6 to 3.2)	3.4 (0.2 to 46.2)
Neuroblastoma	8/2.9	2.8 (1.4 to 5.6)	8.3 (2.8 to 24.4)		2/1.2	1.6 (0.4 to 6.4)	3.6 (0.1 to 143.3)	4/1.0	4.0 (1.5 to 10.8)	12.7 (3.5 to 46.8)
Retinoblastoma	36/4.4	8.3 (6.0 to 11.5)	44.8 (30.9 to 65.0)		20/1.4	13.8 (8.9 to 21.5)	82.1 (51.2 to 131.7)	5/1.5	3.4 (1.4 to 8.1)	17.7 (5.1 to 61.7)
Wilms tumour	13/6.0	2.2 (1.3 to 3.7)	6.4 (2.3 to 17.6)		10/3.7	2.7 (1.5 to 5.0)	11.5 (4.3 to 30.7)	2/1.0	2.1 (0.5 to 8.3)	4.6 (0.3 to 67.1)
Malignant bone tumour:										
Osteosarcoma	5/5.2	1.0 (0.4 to 2.3)	0.0		1/1.8	0.6 (0.1 to 4.0)	0.0	3/1.4	2.2 (0.7 to 6.7)	10.2 (1.3 to 82.8)
Ewing sarcoma	0/1.3	0.0	0.0		0	0.0	0.0	0	0.0	0.0
Soft-tissue sarcoma	17/6.9	2.4 (1.5 to 3.9)	10.8 (4.8 to 24.1)		8/2.3	3.5 (1.8 to 7.0)	18.9 (7.2 to 49.7)	1/1.9	0.5 (0.1 to 3.7)	0.0
Germ cell and gonadal neoplasm ^d	11/4.2	2.6 (1.4 to 4.7)	13.8 (5.3 to 36.2)		1/0.7	1.5 (0.2 to 10.6)	5.1 (0.0 to 2027.1)	4/1.2	3.4 (1.3 to 9.1)	19.1 (4.8 to 76.3)
Other ^e	22/9.5	2.3 (1.5 to 3.5)	11.8 (5.7 to 24.5)		7/1.5	4.5 (2.2 to 9.5)	32.3 (12.5 to 83.5)	4/1.9	2.1 (0.8 to 5.6)	8.6 (1.3 to 55.1)
P-heterogeneity		<.001	<.001			<.001	<.001		.57	.65
Retinoblastoma, Hereditary Status ^{b2}										
Non-heritable	7/2.2	3.2 (1.5 to 6.7)	15.3 (5.2 to 45.1)	1.0 (ref.)	2/0.4	5.6 (1.4 to 22.3)	31.1 (5.7 to 168.3)	3/1.3	2.3 (0.7 to 7.1)	10.2 (1.4 to 75.7)
Heritable	21/1.3	16.5 (10.8 to 25.3)	94.4 (59.9 to 148.9)	5.2 (2.2 to 12.2)	18/1.1	16.7 (10.5 to 26.5)	98.4 (60.2 to 160.9)	2/0.1	13.6 (3.4 to 54.4)	70.9 (15.9 to 316.3)
P-heterogeneity		<.001	<.001	<.001		.21	.26		.19	.27
Treatment era ^{b3}										
<1970	70/30.0	2.3 (1.8 to 3.0)	13.3 (8.8 to 20.1)	1.0 (ref.)	26/10.2	2.5 (1.7 to 3.7)	14.3 (7.6 to 26.9)	10/5.5	1.8 (1.0 to 3.4)	8.4 (2.1 to 33.2)
1970-79	64/25.9	2.5 (1.9 to 3.2)	11.0 (7.3 to 16.5)	1.1 (0.8 to 1.5)	37/13.6	2.7 (2.0 to 3.8)	13.2 (7.9 to 21.9)	13/5.1	2.6 (1.5 to 4.4)	12.2 (5.0 to 29.8)
1980-89	45/22.5	2.0 (1.5 to 2.7)	5.7 (3.2 to 10.3)	0.9 (0.6 to 1.3)	20/9.3	2.1 (1.4 to 3.3)	6.9 (3.0 to 15.6)	10/5.7	1.7 (0.9 to 3.2)	4.5 (1.1 to 19.3)
1990-1999	17/6.1	2.8 (1.7 to 4.5)	5.8 (3.0 to 13.1)	1.2 (0.7 to 2.1)	6/1.6	3.7 (1.7 to 8.3)	10.8 (3.6 to 32.2)	2/1.7	1.2 (0.3 to 4.6)	0.5 (0.0 to 10425.1)
2000-2008	1/0.4	2.4 (0.3 to 16.8)	2.4 (0.1 to 71.8)	1.0 (0.1 to 7.7)	0/0.1	0.0	0.0	0/0.2	0.0	0.0
P-trend		.89	.01	.70		.95	.18		.52	.08

Table 2. (Continued)

Factor	All Survivors				With Radiotherapy ^a			Without Radiotherapy		
	O/E	SIR (95% CI)	AER (95% CI)	RR ^b (95% CI)	O/E	SIR (95% CI)	AER (95% CI)	O/E	SIR (95% CI)	AER (95% CI)
Age at prior treatment ^{b4} (year)										
0-4	84/24.7	3.4 (2.7 to 4.2)	11.3 (8.4 to 15.3)	1.0 (ref.)	49/12.3	4.0 (3.0 to 5.3)	16.7 (11.5 to 24.2)	13/6.3	2.1 (1.2 to 3.6)	4.9 (1.7 to 13.9)
5-9	39/18.7	2.1 (1.5 to 2.9)	7.0 (3.8 to 12.8)	0.8 (0.6 to 1.3)	17/9.8	1.7 (1.1 to 2.8)	5.2 (1.7 to 16.0)	10/4.2	2.4 (1.3 to 4.5)	9.2 (3.2 to 26.6)
10-14	49/25.9	1.9 (1.4 to 2.5)	8.2 (4.5 to 14.8)	0.7 (0.5 to 1.2)	23/11.3	2.0 (1.3 to 3.1)	9.9 (4.4 to 22.1)	10/6.6	1.5 (0.8 to 2.8)	4.9 (0.8 to 30.9)
15-21	25/15.6	1.6 (1.1 to 2.4)	6.6 (2.3 to 18.6)	0.6 (0.3 to 1.0)	0/1.4	0	0	2/1.1	1.8 (0.4 to 7.2)	8.6 (0.4 to 195.8)
P-trend		<.001	.13	.24		<.001	.02		.49	.77
Attained age ^{b5} (year)										
<20	21/3.0	7.0 (4.6 to 10.7)	4.4 (2.7 to 7.3)	1.0 (ref.)	9/1.0	8.7 (4.5 to 16.8)	5.3 (2.5 to 11.1)	3/0.9	3.3 (1.1 to 10.3)	1.9 (0.4 to 9.5)
20-29	49/20.5	2.4 (1.8 to 3.2)	7.0 (4.3 to 11.3)	0.4 (0.2 to 0.6)	25/7.5	3.3 (2.3 to 4.9)	11.2 (6.4 to 19.6)	5/4.6	1.1 (0.5 to 2.6)	0.5 (0.0 to *)
30-39	59/27.9	2.1 (1.6 to 2.7)	12.2 (7.5 to 19.8)	0.3 (0.2 to 0.5)	22/12.1	1.8 (1.2 to 2.8)	9.1 (3.6 to 23.0)	17/5.5	3.1 (1.9 to 4.9)	23.5 (11.6 to 47.6)
40-49	39/19.9	2.0 (1.4 to 2.7)	16.4 (8.6 to 31.0)	0.3 (0.1 to 0.5)	17/8.8	1.9 (1.2 to 3.1)	15.7 (5.9 to 42.0)	7/4.1	1.7 (0.8 to 3.6)	12.4 (2.1 to 72.4)
≥50	29/13.7	2.1 (1.5 to 3.1)	30.6 (15.4 to 60.9)	0.3 (0.1 to 0.6)	16/5.5	2.9 (1.8 to 4.8)	51.4 (24.4 to 108.4)	3/3.1	1.0 (0.3 to 3.0)	0
P-trend		<.001	<.001	<.001		.02	<.001		.37	.05
Chemotherapy ^{b6}										
No	52/23.1	2.2 (1.7 to 3.0)	10.5 (6.4 to 17.1)	1.0 (ref.)	34/13.2	2.6 (1.8 to 3.6)	13.7 (7.9 to 23.8)	18/9.8	1.8 (1.2 to 2.9)	6.8 (2.5 to 18.7)
Yes	62/29.5	2.1 (1.6 to 2.7)	6.2 (3.9 to 10.0)	0.9 (0.5 to 1.6)	43/19.6	2.2 (1.6 to 3.0)	7.5 (4.3 to 13.0)	13/7.6	1.7 (1.0 to 2.9)	3.6 (1.0 to 13.5)
P-heterogeneity		.72	.15	.73		.49	.14		.83	.45
Radiotherapy ^{b6}										
No	35/18.2	1.9 (1.4 to 2.7)	6.0 (3.0 to 11.9)	1.0 (ref.)						
Yes	89/34.9	2.6 (2.1 to 3.1)	11.1 (7.9 to 15.6)	1.7 (1.1 to 2.7)						
P-heterogeneity		.15	.08	.02						

Abbreviations: SIR= standardised incidence ratios; AER= absolute excessive risk; RR= relative risk; SPM=subsequent primary melanoma; O=Observed number; E=Expected number; CI=Confidence Interval; CNS=central nervous system

a: It is notable that treatment data were available for 68% of the total cohort.

b: Relative Risk. For each exposure factor a specific Poisson regression model was applied including different set of confounders. A Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) was designed to guide the potential confounding factors. Country was considered as a random effect in each model. b1: No adjustment required (See: <https://dagitty.net/mHtRRBr55>). b2: No adjustment required (See: <https://dagitty.net/mGy2bhQAf>). b3: No adjustment required (See: <https://dagitty.net/m8u8W5oFt>). b4: RRs were derived from a Poisson regression including age at diagnosis, and type of childhood cancer (See: <https://dagitty.net/mVAmNzxtn>). b5: RRs were derived from a Poisson regression including attained age, type of childhood cancer, decade of childhood cancer, and age at diagnosis (See: <https://dagitty.net/mRGomGpWk>). b6: RRs were derived from a Poisson regression including chemotherapy, radiotherapy, type of childhood cancer, and decade of childhood cancer (See: <https://dagitty.net/mGghodMWs>).

c: NHL=Non-Hodgkins lymphoma Includes 10 Non-Hodgkin's lymphoma and 2 Burkitt lymphoma.

d: Excluded CNS germ cells tumours and added to CNS tumours category.

e: Included 11 observed melanomas in non-melanoma skin cancer, 2 in thyroid carcinomas, 3 in other and unspecified carcinomas, 2 in unspecified lymphomas, 1 in nasopharyngeal carcinoma, 1 in renal carcinoma, 1 in other peripheral nervous cell tumour, 1 in other and unspecified malignant neoplasm.

Table 3. SIR, AER, and RR of SPM without retinoblastoma survivors.

Factor	All survivors				With Radiotherapy ^a			Without Radiotherapy		
	O/E	SIR (95% CI)	AER (95% CI)	RR ^b (95% CI)	O/E	SIR (95% CI)	AER (95% CI)	O/E	SIR (95% CI)	AER (95% CI)
Overall	161/80.5	2.0 (1.7 to 2.3)	6.9 (5.1 to 9.4)		69/33.4	2.1 (1.6 to 2.6)	7.6 (4.8 to 12.1)	30/16.7	1.8 (1.3 to 2.6)	5.1 (2.3 to 11.4)
Sex ^{b1}										
Male	63/33.8	1.9 (1.5 to 2.4)	4.6 (2.7 to 7.9)	1.0 (ref.)	29/14.4	2.0 (1.4 to 2.9)	5.7 (2.8 to 11.8)	9/6.8	1.3 (0.7 to 2.5)	1.6 (0.1 to 22.9)
Female	98/46.7	2.1 (1.7 to 2.6)	9.5 (6.5 to 13.9)	1.1 (0.8 to 1.6)	40/19.0	2.1 (1.5 to 2.9)	9.9 (5.5 to 17.9)	21/9.9	2.1 (1.4 to 3.3)	9.2 (4.1 to 20.7)
P-heterogeneity		.46	.03	.45		.87	.24		.22	.07
Treatment era ^{b2}										
<1970	48/27.1	1.8 (1.3 to 2.3)	7.8 (4.1 to 15.0)	1.0 (ref.)	16/9.2	1.7 (1.1 to 2.8)	6.9 (2.2 to 21.9)	8/4.5	1.8 (0.9 to 3.6)	8.1 (1.7 to 39.4)
1970-79	53/24.9	2.1 (1.6 to 2.8)	8.5 (5.1 to 14.2)	1.1 (0.7 to 1.8)	30/13.3	2.3 (1.6 to 3.2)	9.7 (5.1 to 18.4)	10/4.7	2.1 (1.1 to 3.9)	8.8 (2.7 to 28.6)
1980-89	43/22.0	2.0 (1.4 to 2.6)	5.5 (3.0 to 10.2)	0.9 (0.5 to 1.4)	18/9.2	2.0 (1.2 to 3.1)	5.8 (2.3 to 15.0)	10/5.6	1.8 (1.0 to 3.3)	4.8 (1.2 to 19.7)
1990-1999	17/6.5	2.6 (1.6 to 4.2)	5.4 (2.5 to 11.7)	1.1 (0.5 to 2.1)	5/1.7	2.9 (1.2 to 7.1)	7.5 (2.0 to 28.2)	2/1.9	1.1 (0.3 to 4.2)	0.2 (0.0 to 1.1e+10)
P-trend		.27	.29	.85		.48	.76		.60	.14
Age at prior treatment ^{b3} (year)										
0-4	50/20.7	2.4 (1.8 to 3.2)	6.4 (4.0 to 10.3)	1.0 (ref.)	29/10.9	2.7 (1.8 to 3.8)	9.1 (5.1 to 16.4)	9/4.9	1.8 (1.0 to 3.5)	3.4 (0.8 to 14.4)
5-9	37/18.4	2.0 (1.5 to 2.8)	6.5 (3.4 to 12.3)	0.9 (0.6 to 1.4)	17/9.8	1.7 (1.1 to 2.8)	5.2 (1.7 to 16.0)	9/4.0	2.2 (1.2 to 4.3)	8.0 (2.4 to 26.1)
10-14	49/25.9	1.9 (1.4 to 2.5)	8.2 (4.5 to 14.8)	0.9 (0.5 to 1.4)	23/11.3	2.0 (1.3 to 3.1)	9.9 (4.4 to 22.1)	10/6.6	1.5 (0.8 to 2.8)	4.9 (0.8 to 30.9)
15-21	25/15.6	1.6 (1.1 to 2.4)	6.6 (2.3 to 18.6)	0.7 (0.4 to 1.2)	0/1.4	0	0	2/1.1	1.8 (0.4 to 7.2)	8.6 (0.4 to 195.8)
P-trend		.08	.70	.21		.09	.52		.69	.59
Attained age ^{b4} (year)										
<20	18/2.8	6.3 (4.0 to 10.1)	4.0 (2.3 to 6.9)	1.0 (ref.)	6/1.0	6.1 (2.7 to 13.5)	3.5 (1.4 to 9.2)	3/0.9	3.5 (1.1 to 10.8)	2.1 (0.4 to 10.1)
20-29	42/19.6	2.1 (1.6 to 2.9)	5.7 (3.2 to 10.1)	0.3 (0.2 to 0.6)	21/7.2	2.9 (1.9 to 4.4)	9.1 (4.7 to 17.5)	5/4.4	1.1 (0.5 to 2.7)	0.8 (0.0 to 855.2)
30-39	48/26.6	1.8 (1.4 to 2.4)	8.8 (4.7 to 16.6)	0.3 (0.2 to 0.5)	18/11.7	1.5 (1.0 to 2.4)	6.0 (1.6 to 22.5)	14/5.2	2.7 (1.6 to 4.6)	19.6 (8.5 to 44.9)
40-49	30/18.7	1.6 (1.1 to 2.3)	10.3 (4.0 to 26.6)	0.3 (0.1 to 0.5)	14/8.4	1.7 (1.0 to 2.8)	11.3 (3.1 to 41.6)	5/3.6	1.4 (0.6 to 3.3)	6.5 (0.3 to 159.3)
≥50	23/12.7	1.8 (1.2 to 2.7)	22.0 (8.8 to 54.9)	0.3 (0.1 to 0.6)	10/5.1	2.0 (1.1 to 3.6)	25.6 (7.2 to 91.0)	3/2.7	1.1 (0.4 to 3.5)	3.4 (0.0 to 98057.0)
P-trend		<.001	<.001	.001		.02	.06		.34	.14
Chemotherapy ^{b5}										
No	40/20.9	1.9 (1.4 to 2.6)	7.8 (4.0 to 14.8)	1.0 (ref.)	24/12.3	2.0 (1.3 to 2.9)	8.4 (3.7 to 19.1)	16/8.5	1.9 (1.2 to 3.1)	7.2 (2.5 to 20.4)
Yes	58/29.2	2.0 (1.5 to 2.6)	5.6 (3.3 to 9.4)	0.7 (0.4 to 1.4)	40/19.3	2.1 (1.5 to 2.8)	6.7 (3.7 to 12.3)	12/7.6	1.6 (0.9 to 2.8)	3.0 (0.6 to 14.0)
P-heterogeneity		.86	.46	.34		.82	.68		.64	.33
Radiotherapy ^{b5}										
No	30/16.7	1.8 (1.3 to 2.6)	5.1 (2.3 to 11.4)	1.0 (ref.)						
Yes	69/33.4	2.1 (1.6 to 2.6)	7.6 (4.8 to 12.1)	1.4 (0.8 to 2.2)						
P-heterogeneity		.52	.37	.21						

Abbreviations: SIR= standardised incidence ratios; AER= absolute excessive risk; RR= relative risk; SPM=subsequent primary melanoma; O=Observed number; E=Expected number; CI=Confidence Interval.

a: It is notable that treatment data were available for 68% of the total cohort.

b: Relative Risk. For each exposure factor a specific Poisson regression model was applied including different set of cofounders. A Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) was designed to guide the potential confounding factors. Country was considered as a random effect in each model. b1: No adjustment required (See: <https://dagitty.net/mHiRRBr55>). b2: No adjustment required (See: <https://dagitty.net/m8u8W5oFt>). b3: RRs were derived from a Poisson regression including age at diagnosis, and type of childhood cancer (See: <https://dagitty.net/mVAmNzxtn>). b4: RRs were derived from a Poisson regression including attained age, type of childhood cancer, decade of childhood cancer, and age at diagnosis (See: <https://dagitty.net/mRGomGpWk>). b5: RRs were derived from a Poisson regression including chemotherapy, radiotherapy, type of childhood cancer, and decade of childhood cancer (See: <https://dagitty.net/mGghodMWs>).

Figure legends

Figure 1

Figure 1. Overall cumulative incidence of SPM by attained age.

Abbreviation: SPM = subsequent primary melanoma.

Figure 2

Figure 2. Cumulative incidence of SPM by attained age and type of childhood cancer.

Figure 2. Number at risk and events by attained age group for figure 2

Type of childhood cancer		Attained age					
		0-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60+
Heritable retinoblastoma	Events	3	4	7	2	4	1
	At Risk	713	568	447	280	152	47
Leukaemia	Events	6	11	8	2	2	0
	At Risk	15,836	11,084	6,482	2,374	363	26
Lymphoma	Events	2	9	8	7	2	1
	At Risk	7,154	8,886	5,662	2,917	1,069	291
Other combined	Events	8	17	23	14	13	1
	At Risk	19,031	19,463	13,284	7,237	3,066	929
CNS	Events	2	5	9	7	3	1
	At Risk	12,800	11,201	7,256	4,060	1,845	551

Abbreviation: SPM = subsequent primary melanoma; CNS=central nervous system.

Note:

Values in parentheses denote 95% confidence intervals (CIs).

The “Other combined” category includes neuroblastoma, Wilms tumour, osteosarcoma, soft-tissue sarcoma, germ cell & gonadal neoplasm, non-melanoma skin cancer, thyroid carcinoma, other and unspecified carcinoma, unspecified lymphoma, nasopharyngeal carcinoma, renal carcinoma, other peripheral nervous cell tumour, other and unspecified malignant neoplasm. Non-heritable and unknown heritable status retinoblastoma were excluded from analysis.

The “lymphoma” category includes both Hodgkin lymphoma and non-Hodgkin lymphoma.

Expected cumulative incidence was similar across childhood cancer types, reaching approximately 0.6% by age 60 years.

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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